

PUBLIC AWARENESS OF EXERCISING REGULARLY DURING PRODUCTIVE AGE OF 20-40 YEARS OLD IN THE DIGITAL ERA

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Abstract:

The tendency of declining interest and the desire of the public to do sport activities is very alarming, because it is not comparable with the government's increasingly serious and consistent efforts in the development of sports. The purpose of this study is to know the level of public awareness of sport regularly during productive age of 20-40 years old. This study is a descriptive qualitative research. Sources of data in this study came from interviews and questionnaires. Data analysis was using Likert scale analysis and descriptive data analysis. Based on the observation results obtained data on the level of awareness in exercising regularly in men aged 20-40 years old with the following criteria: high criteria of 20% with the type sport of penchant for football and volleyball, medium criteria of 70% with the type of sport of penchant for football, volleyball and badminton and a low criterion of 10% with the type of badminton and soccer sport of penchant. While the level of awareness in exercising regularly in women aged 20-40 years old with the following criteria: 10% high criteria with gymnastics and volleyball gymnastics, moderate criteria of 75% with badminton, gymnastics and volleyball, while low criteria amounting to 15% with badminton sport type.

Keywords: awareness, community, regular exercise, productive age

1. Introduction

The need for health becomes a very important thing in human life. By exercising, a person can maintain his good health so it will not be easy to get sick. However, of the many people who have heard or have done this activity, few people really understand

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what sports are and realize the benefits of exercise. Yarmak et al. (2017) stated that, *"The positive effect of physical activity is expressed in the normalization of the functional and morphological state of the body, increase of the physical condition and working capacity, the general physical condition of the persons involved"*.

The benefits of exercise can be felt by each individual. These benefits include helping to protect against high blood pressure, obesity, back pain, and able to improve mood and reduce stress. Apart from the benefits that have been mentioned, sports can also form the muscles that exist in the human body either who want a muscular body shape it can also keep the body's stamina to always stay healthy.

Public awareness of the importance of regular exercise today is still considered less, especially during productive age between 20-40 years old. During productive age, many people who often ignore important activities in exercise because of their busy activities. Their busy activities in achieving the welfare of life often ignore the importance of a person in maintaining health. Busyness is often the cause of someone to be lazy in exercising. Ahmaed et al. (2016) stated that, *"Screens (television, videos, computers, video games, mobile phones) are all around us, and "screen time" is an important component of daily life, which excessively hampers regular participation in games, sports and activity-based recreational programmes"*. Exercise can improve physical fitness. By having a good physical fitness, then someone will be able to do daily activities without feeling tired that means. Sukarmin & Sudardiyono (2017) stated that, *"Physical fitness development should always be a priority if a person (i.e., a student) does not want to experience difficulty in"*. McArdle et al. (2001) stated that, *"Physical fitness has been defined as the result of body movement that is generated by muscle action that increases energy expenditure"*. This will affect physical fitness. A good level of fitness as a result of regular physical exercise, and in low to moderate doses, will affect cognitive functions, such as (1) ability to remember, (2) solve problems of numbers, (3) accuracy (Wirnantika, Pratama & Hanief, 2017).

Society must be aware that sport (physical activity) is very beneficial for the health of each individual. Physical activity is known to be an important factor in promoting health and physical efficiency (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2010; Janssen & LeBlanc, 2010).

The level of public awareness in exercise can be determined using the sports development index (SDI). This index is calculated based on the index of participation, open space, human resources, and fitness. In one study (Mutohir and Maksum, 2007) the Sport Development Index (SDI) is a composite index that reflects the success of sports development based on four basic dimensions, including (a) open spaces available for sport, (b) human resources or sporting personnel involved in sports activities, (c) citizen participation to exercise regularly and (d) the degree of physical fitness achieved by the community.

The productive age community ranged 18 - 45 years old, an age where humans are mature physically and biologically. At this age, the human being is at the peak of its activity. Physical activity performed tends to be heavier than other ages. Dense activity

often triggers the onset of stress which is also a disease that often descend the community. Stress is a feeling experienced when a person thinks that *“the demands exceed the personal and social resources the individual is able to mobilize”* (Lazarus, 1966). The onset of stress can alter normal body functions and over long periods of time leading to the emergence of symptoms of degenerative diseases.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Participants

This study is a descriptive research to determine the independent variable value (either one or more variables) without comparing or relating the variables (Hanief & Himawanto, 2017). The subjects of this study were productive age society at the age of 20 - 40 years old in Paron Village, Bagor Sub-district, Nganjuk District, East Java Province, Indonesia about 677 people consisting of 331 men and 346 women. The sampling technique used was purposive random sampling, so the sample used was 350 people consisting of 175 men and 175 women.

2.2 Procedure

This research uses three stages, namely pre-field stage, field work stage, and data analysis phase. This research was conducted in July 2017. Data source in this research is primary and secondary data obtained through interview and filling questionnaire by the community. Data analysis technique was done by analyzing data with Likert scale. The questionnaire distributed was using Likert scale and used to determine the subject of the interview in this study. Data analysis used were in three models, namely: (1) fixed comparison method; (2) data analysis method according to Spradley; and (3) data analysis method according to Miles and Huberman (Moleong, 2014). In this study, the researcher used a fixed comparison method. According to Moleong (2014) suggested that the so-called fixed comparison method because in the data analysis, constantly comparing one datum with another datum, and then consistently compare the categories with other categories. The process of data analysis includes: data reduction, data categorization, synthesizing, and ended by compiling work hypothesis.

3. Results and Discussion

A. R summarizing the results of the public awareness questionnaire can be expressed in the form of diagrams as follows:

Table 1: Summary of Questionnaire Results

Criteria	Total Point of Questionnaire	Percentage
High	52	15%
Intermediate	254	72.5%
Low	44	12.5%
Total	350	100%

Table 1 shows that the level of awareness in regular exercise both men and women with high criterion of 15%, medium criterion that is equal to 72,5%, and low equal to 12,5%. The level of awareness in regular exercise of both men and women can be presented in the following diagram:

Figure 1: Level of awareness in regular exercise both men and women

B. A summary of the results of the public awareness questionnaires in men and women can be expressed in diagrammatic form as follows:

Table 2: Analysis of Questionnaires on Men and Women

Criteria	Men		Women	
	Total Point of Questionnaire	Percentage	Total Point of Questionnaire	Percentage
High	35	20%	18	10%
Intermediate	122	70%	131	75%
Low	18	10%	26	15%
Total	175	100%	175	100%

Table 2 shows that the level of awareness in exercising regularly in men with high criteria of 20%, intermediate criterion that is equal to 70%, and low by 10%, while the level of awareness in regular exercise in women with high criteria of 10% intermediate criteria of 75%, and low by 15%.

The level of awareness in regular exercise in both men and women can be presented in the following diagram:

Figure 2: The percentage level of awareness in regular exercise in men and women

C. Type of Sports Desired by Society

Table 3: Type of Sports for Desired by the People in Paron Village, Bagor Sub-district, Nganjuk District

No.	Type of Sport	Percentage
1	Soccer	32.5 %
2	Volleyball	25 %
3	Badminton	27.5 %
4	Gymnastics	15 %
Total		100 %

Table 3 shows that the type of sports for the people of Paron Village, Bagor Sub-district, Nganjuk District is dominated by soccer amounting to 32.5%, 25% volleyball, 27.5% badminton and 15%.

Figure 3: Type of Sports for Desired by the People

This study aims to know the level of public awareness of exercise regularly during productive age of 20-40 years. Level of awareness in regular exercise both men and women in productive age 20-40 years with high criterion of 15%, intermediate criterion that is equal to 72,5%, and low criterion equal to 12,5%. High criteria are filled with soccer, volleyball, and gymnastics. The intensity of time, frequency and hobbies make people on this high criterion do these types of sports regularly. In a week, this

sport can be done in the frequency of five to seven days with a minimum time intensity of 30 minutes. In various busyness and many other factors people on this criteria still spend time in exercising % and gymnastics as much as 15%.

While intermediate criteria is filled with the type of football, volleyball, badminton and also gymnastics. The intensity of time, frequency and hobbies make people on this intermediate criterion do these types of sports regularly. In a week, this sport can be done in a frequency of three to five days on a regular basis with a minimum time intensity of 30 minutes.

While the low criteria is filled with the type of football and badminton. The intensity of time, frequency and hobby keeps people on this low criterion of do these types of sports regularly. In a week, this sport can be done in the frequency of one to two days on a regular basis with a minimum time intensity of 30 minutes.

The level of public awareness in exercising regularly, especially women society aged 20-40 years old has a high level of awareness of 10% with gymnastics and volleyball, medium criteria of 75% with badminton, gymnastics and volleyball sport type while low criteria of 15% with the type of badminton.

The level of awareness in regular exercise, especially male society with the following criteria: high criterion of 20% with the type of sport of penchant for football and volleyball, medium criteria of 70% with the type of soccer, volleyball and badminton and low criterion of 10% with the type of badminton and soccer.

If the two sexes (male and female) of the questionnaire are compared then it is known that the level of awareness in exercise is considered important by the male community with a ratio of 20% compared to women of 10% only. However, in the middle criteria, women are superior to men by 75% and men by 70%. On the lower criterion of men by 10% and women by 15%, so it can be concluded that men have more attitude awareness in exercising than women. Because men are usually more active in the appeal of women, such as coming home from work, school or other activities men usually always self-centered to exercise in the afternoon after activities in the morning until noon, but most women prefer at home, watch TV and take care other work.

Types of community sports favorites in Paron Village Bagor Sub-district Nganjuk district is dominated by football as much as 32.5%, volleyball as much as 25%, badminton as much as 27.5% and gymnastics as much as 15%. This sport is done regularly and together with members of the community in Paron Village Bagor Sub-district Nganjuk District.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that the level of public awareness of regular exercise at the productive age of 20-40 years old in Paron Village Bagor Sub-district Nganjuk District said that the results of research most show a good level of awareness on men or women. Whereas if by sex, men have a higher level of awareness compared with awareness in women.

After knowing the result of research then obtained implication for the people of Paron Village Bagor Sub-district Nganjuk District, the community can use result of this research: that regular exercise is important, especially during 20-40 years old to avoid diseases.

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